

Use of High Frequency Oscillometer in the Determination of Cations with Phosphates as Precipitants

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Estimations of aluminium, cadmium, zinc, manganese, and magnesium have been carried out in aqueous or ethanol-water medium, using a 30 Mc high frequency titrimeter unit. Disodium phosphate has been used for magnesium ions, whereas diammonium phosphate has been used for others. In case of aluminium and cadmium, the breaks are not so sharp as in other cases. Conditions suitable for quantitative estimations of the above ions have been worked out.

High frequency titration technique of quantitative analysis, although a recent one¹, has been applied to a wide variety of reactions. Apart from the use of many organic precipitants and complexing agents for determination of different cations, several inorganic reactions, such as, argentometric and mercurimetric titrations of chloride and thiocyanate^{2,3}, determination of sulphate with standard barium nitrate⁴, and determination of thorium with oxalate⁵ have been investigated.

The authors have recently reported the determination of some cations using potassium chromate as the precipitant⁶. No work seems to have been done with phosphates as precipitants except for the determination of uranium⁷ by using diammonium hydrogen phosphate. Anderson and Revinson⁸ in high frequency titrimetric determination of beryllium with sodium hydroxide have mentioned that although the results by using triammonium phosphate as a titrant are quantitative, the breaks are not sharp. They have offered, however, no other information regarding the nature of the curves and the results. The object of the present investigation is to collect information on the use of phosphates as titrants in the high frequency estimations of metal ions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The instrument used was described by the authors in their earlier communication⁶. All the chemicals used were of the reagent quality and all solutions were prepared in conductivity water.

The effective component method⁶ was used in all the titrations except in the case of manganese, for which the deflection method was used. In the deflection method, the titrimeter is brought to resonance only once and any changes in the properties of the solu-

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2. Bladel and Malmstadt, *Anal. Chem.*, 1950, **22**, 1410.
3. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1950, **22**, 1413.
4. Milner, *ibid.*, 1952, **24**, 1247.
5. Bladel and Malmstadt, *ibid.*, 1951, **23**, 471.
6. Kumar and Singh, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1963, **57A**, 79.
7. Silva, *Rev. Port. Equim.*, 1958, No. 1, 61-72.
8. *Anal. Chem.*, 1950, **22**, 1272.

tion are indicated on the milliammeter scale, without further alterations in the controls of the apparatus, as the mixed effect of the resulting capacitance and the resulting conductance of the measuring cell. To improve the end points, "out of tune" technique was employed in the case of manganese. In this technique, the resonance synchronisation of the titrimer with the specimen is discorded to a predetermined extent. The extent of discording (+20 divisions of the condenser scale) had to be determined by performing several experiments.

As the high frequency titrimeters show maximum sensitivity over certain ranges of concentration in the case of conducting solutions, concentrations of the solutions were suitably adjusted. The ranges of concentration for maximum sensitivity were determined experimentally in each case.

In case of magnesium and zinc, addition of ethanol was found necessary to obtain sharp end points.

Effect of pH.—Adjustment of pH was found essentially necessary because of the small differences between the pHs at which the various phosphate precipitates began to separate and the pHs at which the corresponding hydroxides began to be precipitated. For example, in the case of aluminium, the phosphate began to separate at pH 3.79 and the corresponding hydroxide at pH 4.14. pH of the aqueous solution of aluminium sulphate used was 3.5. To raise the pH for complete precipitation of aluminium phosphate, a requisite quantity of ammonium acetate was added and the pH was adjusted at 4.1. This pH was slightly higher than the minimum at which the phosphate of aluminium began to be precipitated. This was necessary because during the titration addition of diammonium hydrogen phosphate decreased the pH of the solution in the initial stages due to liberation of free acid which was later neutralised by addition of more of diammonium hydrogen phosphate. The lowering of pH in the initial stages of addition of the phosphate was observed in other cases as well. Consequently, pH in each case was adjusted at a slightly higher value than the minimum pH at which the corresponding phosphate began to be precipitated. For estimation of magnesium, disodium hydrogen phosphate was used due to its higher pH, as magnesium ammonium phosphate is precipitated only in alkaline media. For all other estimations, diammonium hydrogen phosphate solution of pH 7.8 was used.

The regions of maximum sensitivity, pH, medium, and the foreign electrolytes added are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Metal ion.	*Conc. of salt in 60 ml (aq. medium).	pH.	Medium.	Foreign electrolyte added to adjust pH.
Mg ²⁺ in MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	25.75mg.	10.3	1:1 Ethanol : water	NH ₄ OH+1 ml of (1M) NH ₄ Cl**
Mn ²⁺ in MnSO ₄ ·4H ₂ O	23.90	6.5	Water	Ammonium acetate
Zn ²⁺ in ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	60-180	7.2	1:1 Ethanol : water	NH ₄ OH+10ml of (1M)NH ₄ Cl**
Al ³⁺ in Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃ ·18H ₂ O	30-80	4.1	Water	Ammonium acetate
Cd ²⁺ in Cd(NO ₃) ₂	20.70	6.0	Water	None

*for maximum sensitivity.

**To prevent precipitation of the metal hydroxide.

For manganese, magnesium, and cadmium ions, reverse titrations were also performed, but were not successful. In case of cadmium and aluminium, addition of ethanol did not improve the end points.

FIG. 1

A—Direct titration of Al^{3+} (0.0033M, 60 ml) / $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ (0.1M).

B—Reverse titration.

FIG. 2

A—Titration of Al^{3+} (0.0217M, 60ml) / $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ (0.1M).

B—Titration of Zn^{2+} (0.0083M, 60 ml) / $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ (0.1M).

Shapes of titration curves are recorded in Figs. 1 to 3; the results, percentage errors, and the formulas of the compounds precipitated are recorded in Table II. The concentrations of some of the metal ions chosen were different from those recorded in Table I. The concentrations were changed because of the addition of foreign electrolytes or ethanol.

TABLE II

Metal ion estimated.	Metal ion present.	Metal ion found.	% Error.	*Compound precipitated.
Mg²⁺	12.160 mg.	12.115 mg.	0.36	MgNH_4PO_4
	12.160	12.160	0.00	
	14.502	14.483	0.75	
Mn^{2+}	27.470	27.402	0.08	MnNH_4PO_4
	38.456	38.567	0.29	
	38.456	38.574	0.30	
	43.952	43.952	0.00	
Al^{3+}	2.698	2.698	0.00	AlPO_4
	4.047	4.047	0.00	
	7.014	7.014	0.00	
Cd^{2+}	22.482	23.360	0.50	$\text{Cd}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$
	33.723	33.723	0.00	
Zn^{2+}	6.838	6.838	0.00	ZnNH_4PO_4
	6.838	6.838	0.00	
	10.257	10.240	0.13	

*Formulas deduced from titration curves.

As shown in Table II, the results of estimations are quite accurate, provided that the metal ion concentration is within certain limits.

In the case of zinc, the scale readings are nearly constant in the initial stages of the titration (Fig. 2, curve B). The flat portion is followed by a fall in the scale readings. This behaviour may be due to the fact that ammonium chloride concentration being high in the zinc solution, the change in conductance is negligible in the initial stages of the addition of phosphate, whereas it becomes appreciable when all the zinc is precipitated and more of phosphate is added.

FIG. 3

A—Titration of Mn^{2+} (0.017M, 60 ml) / $(NH_4)_2HPO_4$ (0.1M).

B—Titration of Mg^{2+} (0.00833M, 60 ml) / $(NH_4)_2HPO_4$ (0.1M)

Attempts have also been made to determine zirconium and thorium ions in their salt solutions, but the curves obtained are complicated and appear to indicate the formation of more than one compound. Detailed investigations concerning the effect of change of conditions on the nature of the titration curves and other physico-chemical investigations to establish the nature of the compounds, which appear to be precipitated under different conditions, are in progress.

Interferences.—No detailed investigations of the effect of foreign cations on the titration curves were made. It is normally assumed that all the cations, which form insoluble phosphates at the specified pHs, must be absent.

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